

<App Name> App Instruction Manual

Part 1: Installation

Open the App Store on your Apple Watch.

Click "Search" and enter "<App Name>" through scribble or dictation.

Link: <App Link>

Install the app by clicking the blue download icon on the right.

Part 2: Setup

Open the <App Name> app on your Apple Watch.

You will be prompted to allow notifications. Please allow notifications, as they are essential to the study.

Note: If you missed the notifications pop-over, please see Appendix 1 before continuing with the setup.

You will be greeted with the above screen.

Please press firmly (“force touch”) on the text at the top.

Click on “User Settings” to open the settings page.

Please set your User ID.

Please enter your assigned ID into the app and confirm by pressing OK at the bottom left.

Please set your workday start time.

Please select one of the predefined options.

Note: If you do not start work at any of the presented options, please choose the nearest option after your actual start time.

Please do the same for your workday end time.

Please select all days on which you work.

Please set your desired notification time. This is when you will receive a notification (and email) to fill out your daily or weekly survey. It is up to you if you would like to fill out those surveys right when you end work, or if you would like to do so later in the evening.

Click "Save User Settings". The setup is now complete.

You can now exit the app by pressing the crown on the side of the Apple Watch.

You will receive a notification when it is time to fill out a quick self-report questionnaire.

Part 3: Using the app

Click on "GO!" to start the self-report questionnaire.

Note: If you currently do not have time to fill out the questionnaire, you can press the postpone button.

To select your answer you can use the crown on the side of the Apple Watch to scroll through answer options.

Note: If you did not work during the past hour, please click "I didn't work".

The final screen. You can close the app by pressing the crown on the side of the Apple Watch. You will receive a notification when it is time to fill out the next questionnaire.

Appendix 1: Notifications

In case you missed the notifications prompt on your Apple Watch, please open the "Watch" App on your **iPhone**.

Please scroll down to the "Notifications" tab and click on it.

Please find the <App Name> app in the list of all applications installed.

Select "Allow Notifications" and please turn on sound.

Return to the Setup step.

Appendix 2: Focus Mode

In case you are using the new “Focus mode” feature while working, please allow <App Name> to keep showing you notifications while being in focus. Follow the steps below to add <App Name> as an exception:

Tap on the focus icon.

Click on the three dots on the right.

Click on “Settings”.

Click on "Apps".

Click on the "+" sign and add <App Name> to the allowed apps.

We thank you for your participation in this study. Should you have questions or need assistance at any time, please do not hesitate to reach out to <PI Name, Email>.